

D1.2. Quality assurance and risk management plan & activities Part A

S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]

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ThrombUS+ Consortium

ATHENA	Research and Innovation Center in Information, Communication and Knowledge Technologies, Greece	Eleni Kaldoudi kaldoudi@med.duth.gr
KTU	Kaunas University of Technology Lithuania	Vaidotas Marozas vaidotas.marozas@ktu.lt
VERMON	Vermont SA France	Mathieu Legros m.legros@vermon.com
FRAUNHOFER	Institute for Photonic Microsystems, Fraunhofer Germany	Marco Kircher Marco.kircher@ipms.fraunhofer.de
TELEMED	Telemed Ultrasound Medical Systems Lithuania	Dmitry Novikov d.novikov@pcultrasound.com
EchoNous	EchoNous Inc USA	Pavlos Moustakidis pavlos.moustakidis@echonous.com
MEDIS	medis Medizinische Messtechnik GmbH Germany	Susann Balling sb@medis.company
ComfTech	ComfTech SLR Italy	Lara Alessia Moltani alessia.moltani@comftech.com
TAU	Faculty of Medicine and Health Technology Tampere University, Finland	Antti Vehkaoja antti.vehkaoja@tuni.fi
LMSU	Lithuanian University of Health Science Lithuania	Andrius Macas andrius.macas@lsmu.lt
GNP	Papageorgiou General Hospital Greece	Maria Bigaki pmo@papageorgiou-hospital.gr
CSS-IRCCS	Home Relief of Suffering Hospital Italy	Elvira Grandone e.grandone@operapadrepio.it
HSV	Simon Veil Hospital France	Maxime Gautier maxime.gautier@ch-simoneveil.fr
VDE	Association for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies, Germany	Thorsten Prinz thorsten.prinz@vde.com
MEDEA	MEDEA SRL Italy	Pietro Dionisio p.dionisio@medeaproject.eu
PHAZE	Clinical Research and Pharma Consulting SA Greece	Spiros Anagnostopoulos spiros.anagnostopoulos@phazeclinical.com
PBY	PredictBy Research and Consulting SL Spain	Frans Folkvord ffolkvord@predictby.com
SciGen	SciGen Technologies SA Greece	Katerina Pavlidi katerina.pavlidi@scigentech.com

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Responsible Partner:	ATHENA
Authors:	S. Didaskalou [ATHENA], E. Kaldoudi [ATHENA]
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About ThrombUS+

Deep vein thrombosis (DVT) is the formation of a blood clot within the deep veins, most commonly those of the lower limbs, causing obstruction of blood flow. In 50% of people with DVT, the clot eventually breaks off and travels to the lung to cause pulmonary embolism. Clinical assessment of DVT is notoriously unreliable because up to 2/3 of DVT episodes are clinically silent and patients are symptom free even when pulmonary embolism has developed. Early diagnosis of DVT is crucial and despite the progress made in ultrasound imaging and plethysmography techniques, there is a need for new methods to enable continuous monitoring DVT diagnosis at the point of care.

ThrombUS+ brings together an interdisciplinary team of industrial, technology, regulatory, social science and clinical trial experts to develop a novel wearable diagnostic device for point-of-care, operator free, continuous monitoring in patients with high DVT risk. The device will combine autonomous, AI driven DVT detection based on novel wearable ultrasound hardware, impedance plethysmography and light reflection rheography for immediate detection of blood clot formation in the lower limb. Activity and other physiological measurements will be used to provide a continuous assessment of DVT risk and support DVT prevention via serious gaming. The aggregated data will drive an intelligence decision support unit that will provide accurate monitoring and alerts. Extended reality will be used to guide experts to design exercises and patients to use the device optimally.

ThrombUS+ is intended for use by postoperative patients in the ward, during long surgical operations, cancer patients or otherwise bedridden patients at home or in care units, and women during pregnancy and postpartum. ThrombUS+ will use big data sets for AI training collected in the project via 3 large scale clinical studies and will validate the outcome in the clinical setting via 1 early feasibility study and 1 multi-center clinical trial.

Deliverable D1.2 Description

The deliverable will include a report detailing the quality assurance and risk management plan and any respective templates for the monitoring and reporting of project quality assurance and risks. The final version of the deliverable (Part B, delivered on M42) will also include any updates and an outline of related activities during the project. Output of Task 1.3.

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Terms and Definitions Terms and Definitions

Term	Definition
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
EEA	Ethics External Advisor
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GA	General Assembly (when within the context of project management procedure)
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MS	Microsoft®
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
QA	Quality Assurance
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Risk Management
RP	Reporting Period
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
SEN	Sensitive – refers to the nature of the deliverable.
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive Summary

The aim of the project quality assurance and risk management plan is to set the rules and responsibilities of the partners aimed at ensuring good quality and progress of the work. The document and its respective annexes define activities and procedures necessary to ensure that the quality requirements of the project are met. It also defines policies for identifying threats and for implementing corrective actions. Annexes to the Deliverable include a list of risks identified at project initiation and a number of templates for project documents. However, Annexes are not part of this Publishable Summary.

This document will be updated, when necessary, through the duration of the project extending the information given, including relevant issues and changes in the project or procedures. Each time the document is updated, all partners will be duly informed about the updates and the changes made with respect to the previous version.

A publishable summary of this document is available from the project website.

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Deliverable is overruled by Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement with its possible addendums.

This document is a publishable summary of the deliverable.

1. Quality Assurance Plan

1.1. Quality assurance objectives

The scope of the Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) is to establish the roles, procedures, and tools which are necessary to ensure that the ThrombUS+ project is implemented smoothly and that all project outputs, especially deliverables and periodic reports, are of high quality and submitted on time. Quality assurance addresses the following:

- project’s deliverables, including reports and all other type of deliverables,
- projects documents and other resources, including, documents templates, presentation templates, naming conventions, document versioning,
- handling changes during the course of the project, including changes in submitted deliverables, changes in detailed WP/Task work plan, changes in the Description of Action (DoA) and changes in the consortium and team,
- project processes, including meetings organization and coordination.

To this end the objectives on the quality assurance procedure is to:

- define clear project managerial roles and responsibilities within the ThrombUS+ consortium,
- define the coordination and communication processes,
- define potential risks and evaluate their impact on the execution of the several tasks of the project,
- define risk mitigation measures to guarantee a smooth and proper implementation of the various project’s tasks.

The quality assurance plan will be updated throughout the duration of the project, if deemed necessary, to ensure that roles, procedures and tools, align with the project’s needs.

1.2. Quality assurance principles

ThrombUS+ quality management is built on the principles¹ of the ISO 9000 standards family:

Principle 1 – Customer focus: *“Meet customer requirements and strive to exceed customer expectations.”*

The project follows this principle in the design of the research and development methodology (see involvement of various stakeholders in the detailed work plan) and in the overall project management procedures. In specific, the intended ‘customers’ of ThrombUS+ results are primarily patients and health care systems, and also researchers (academics and private sector) for the uptake and further advancement of the project results. The consortium was assembled to represent a good part of these stakeholders. Moreover, the higher management of the project foresees input from and close collaboration with the Stakeholder Advisory Board with high profile representatives from all scientific domains pertaining to the project, including patients.

Principle 2 – Leadership: *“Establish unity of purpose and direction, create and maintain appropriate working environment.”*

The management structure of the project, information flow and communication patterns, decision making and conflict resolution, as detailed in Grant Agreement Part B and Consortium Agreement have been designed to achieve a clear leadership pyramid structure with a unifying Coordinator at the top,

¹ ISO, Quality Management Principles, ISO Central Secretariat, Geneva, Switzerland, ISBN 978-92-67-10573-4

communicating with a General Assembly consisting of one representative from each partner. This ensures that leadership unity at project level is readily transferred to leadership unity at beneficiary level. The detailed technical work plan and the risk management plan enhance the unity of purpose and direction. Also, communication and conflict resolution strategies as well as addressing gender aspects in a dedicated task (T8.5) build towards creating and maintaining an internal fulfilling working environment.

Principle 3 – Involvement of people: *“Full involvement of people at all levels.”*

The project management structure is indeed a full pyramid, involving people at all levels. The work is organized at the lower level of the Task, thus achieving full involvement of all members of the beneficiaries’ individual teams.

Principle 4 – Process approach: *“Manage activities and resources as processes.”*

Project work plan (including person effort and other resources) has been constructed as individual processes (Tasks) interacting through clear interfaces (denoted as “input from” and “output to” in the descriptions of individual Tasks) and with clear results, i.e. project deliverables with clear one-to-one correspondence to individual Tasks.

Principle 5 – System approach to management: *“Identify and manage interrelated processes as a system.”*

Project Management work package is designed as a horizontal activity that identifies and clusters similar processes to harmonize and integrate management throughout the project. Furthermore, the quality assurance procedures described in this document follow this same principle.

Principle 6 – Continual improvement: *“Continual improvement of the organization’s performance.”*

Quality assurance plan, risk management, detailed WP/Task work plans and peer-reviewing procedures as described in this document aim at ensuring an improvement of the project’s performance.

Principle 7 – Factual approach to decision making: *“Data analysis to support effective decisions.”*

The decision-making process of the project is designed to take into account factual records. Characteristic examples include the process for change management, which sets the procedure for informed and recorded process for decisions that relate to changes in deliverables, work plan, consortium and DoA.

Figure 1. The quality assurance process within ThrombUS+.

The Quality Assurance Plan is a continuous process and is based on the PDCA Cycle (Plan-Do-Check-Act) introduced by W. Edwards Deming² and shown in Figure 1:

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/PDCA>

- **Plan:** is related to the objectives, processes, tools and resources needed to deliver the results according to the work plan and the project requirements.
- **Do:** refers to implementing and carrying out the planned work of the previous step.
- **Check:** refers to monitoring and evaluating the project outcomes and services based on the planned work and the requirements.
- **Act:** refers to the actions taken, if necessary, to make corrections and improve outcomes and performance.

1.3. Roles and Responsibilities

The quality management team follows the overall management structure of the project which was outlined in detail in D1.1 - Management Guide and Collaboration Infrastructure.

Work package leaders hold the overall responsibility for the quality of work, the collaboration process, and the outcome of deliverables within their leading WP. Each work package leader is responsible for overseeing the work package’s deliverables production procedures. Additionally, each WPL is responsible for identifying potential risks and implementing mitigation strategies. If a problem arises, the WP Leader is responsible to timely inform the Project Manager and at the same time take necessary actions to resolve or mitigate the problem.

Task leaders are responsible for executing work within the task, the collaboration processes, and the on-time delivery of the deliverable(s) they are leading. Each Task Leader is responsible for carrying out the necessary procedures for producing the deliverables expected of the specific task following the formal procedure for peer review and quality control presented in this document. Also, each Task Leader is responsible for identifying potential risks and applying mitigation measures. If a problem arises, the Task Leader should timely inform the corresponding WPL and at the same time take necessary actions to resolve the problem.

The Project Coordinator supervises the overall deliverable production process of the project. Should a problem arise, the PC is responsible to timely inform and/or assemble the GA and at the same time take necessary actions to resolve or mitigate the problem.

In case of a failure in any of the responsibilities described above, the PC and the GA is informed and the person failing is substituted or their responsibilities are passed on according to Table 1.

Table 1. Substitutes for potential failure of the responsible person.

Responsible	Substitute
Task Leader	WP Leader
WP Leader	Project Coordinator
Project Manager	Project Coordinator
Project Coordinator	GA

2. Project deliverables

Task Leaders are responsible for organizing and coordinating the team working on the task. The partner responsible for each deliverable coordinates the development of the deliverable and the corresponding report, and, if the deliverable is of sensitive nature (SEN), the publishable summary. The deliverable preparation and peer-review process is described below.

1. At the start of each Task, the TL compiles a detailed task work plan. PM compiles a Deliverable Preparation Plan. The PM is responsible for monitoring the entire process based on these timeframes and report to the respective WPL, PC and GA in case of deviations from the planned deadlines.
2. The WPL coordinates the compilation of the working team for the work package while the TL for the individual task and the respective deliverable(s) in agreement with the DoA. Also, coordinates the identification of the persons acting as reviewers from each of the Partners designated as deliverable reviewers.
3. If required, TL circulates an initial outline of the deliverable to consortium members, requesting input, information, and comments. The Task Leader coordinates the revision of the deliverable's outline by incorporating input and comments. This is optional and is advisable for deliverables that involve extensive collaborative work.
4. The Task Leader initiates the deliverable review process by sharing the deliverable draft to the assigned reviewers. Assigned reviewers are generally members of the ThrombUS+ project, not directly or heavily involved in the specific deliverable. If deemed necessary, (either by the WPL, or the PC or the GA), deliverable reviewing can be assigned to members of the external Stakeholder Advisory Board.
5. The reviewers submit their reviews. The review is mainly the deliverable file with corrections, suggestions and comments indicated with track changes and the Deliverable Review Form with the reviewer's decision. If the reviewer suggests major changes, these are summarized in the comments section of the Review Form.
6. The TL coordinates the revision of the deliverable based on reviewers' comments.
7. Task leader submits the revised version to WPL and PC for acceptance, together with the Author Response Form. If an additional revision is required, steps 5-7 are repeated.
8. The final accepted version is submitted to the PM for editing, ensuring presentation uniformity and for monitoring purposes.
9. The PC submits the deliverable to EC.
10. The PM publishes the deliverable on the project website. If the deliverable is characterized as sensitive (SEN), the TL in collaboration with the PC also prepare a publishable version of the deliverable to be published on the project website.
11. The TL is notified by the PM/PC that the deliverable is submitted and published.
12. In case of major conflict in the reviews (e.g. if authors and reviewers disagree), the deliverable is discussed in the GA and appropriate actions are taken. In this case, the deliverable is accepted when the consensus report is achieved. The person responsible for achieving consensus is the WPL, and then the PC.

3. Project Meetings

Several meetings will be organized throughout the project's duration as shown in Table 2. While these meetings are primarily planned for in-person attendance, virtual participation will also be facilitated for partners unable to attend in person.

A list of all project meetings (including upcoming meetings) is continuously updated by the PM and the Chairperson of each meeting and is available to all project members.

Table 2. Meetings to be organized within the ThrombUS+ project.

Meeting	Timing	Participants
General Assembly	Every 6 months	GA members
Consortium Meetings	Every 6 months	Project consortium members
Periodic Review Meetings	Every 18 months	Representative team members appointed by each partner
Technical Meetings	As needed and called for by WP leaders and Task leaders	Team members working on a particular WP/task, PC, PM

3.1. General Assembly Meetings

The GA is the decision-making of the consortium, as described in the Consortium Agreement and D1.1. The Project coordinator shall chair all meetings of the GA, unless decided otherwise by the GA. The GA consists of one representative from each Party (i.e. 18 Members, see ThrombUS+ D1.1 – Management Guide and Collaboration Infrastructure). Any Member should be present or represented at any meeting, may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting and shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the GA at least once every six months and shall convene extraordinary GA meetings at any time upon written request of any Member. For ordinary meetings, the chairperson should inform each Member as soon as possible, but no later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting. For extraordinary meetings, the chairperson should inform each Member as soon as possible but no later than those 7 days preceding the meeting. Within the same timeframes, the chairperson should send the GA meeting agenda to each Member. Any Agenda item requiring a decision by the Members must be identified as such on the agenda and any member may add items to the original agenda by written notice to all other Members, no later than 7 and 2 days preceding an ordinary and extraordinary meeting, respectively. During a GA meeting, additional agenda items may be added to the original agenda (CA §6.3.2).

Quorum is reached when 2/3 of Members are present or represented. i.e. 12 Members, and the decisions are taken by a majority of the voting cast. If the quorum is not reached, the GA shall convene another ordinary GA meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting quorum is not reached once more, the Chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting, which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum is reached (CA §6.3.4.1).

GA meetings shall coincide with Project Consortium Meetings or be held virtually, utilizing the MS Teams platform.

3.2. Project consortium meetings

Project Consortium meetings are to be scheduled at intervals of about 6 months. An estimated 8 Project Consortium Meetings are planned to be organized, including the kick-off meeting (M01). All members can participate in Project Consortium Meetings, that will serve as major working meetings, for exchanging information, assessment of project's progress (financial, scientific/ technical, and operational wise) and for taking major decision about the projects' implementation. Technical and coordination decision taking during Project Consortium Meetings will be subject to voting, with one voting per present partner, with 2/3 majority required. Such decisions may not contradict GA decisions and may be annulled by the GA.

The PM shall compile the meeting agenda in collaboration with PC and GA and give a written notice by email to all intended participants, as soon as possible but not later than 14 calendar days preceding the meeting. Any Consortium Member may add an item to the original meeting agenda, by notifying all other Consortium members, not later than 7 days preceding the meeting. During the meeting all Members can unanimously agree to add additional items to the original agenda.

The PM shall produce meeting minutes and share the draft to all Consortium members within 10 calendar days of the meeting. The minutes shall be considered as accepted if within 15 calendar days from draft receipt, no Member has objected in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the minutes draft. The PM shall send the finalized minutes to all meeting participants and the GA. The minutes shall be the formal record of the meeting.

3.3. Technical and other Informal Meetings

Technical and bilateral meetings shall be scheduled when deemed necessary. These types of meetings shall be convened and chaired by a WPL or a TL, or other team member as necessary. The chairperson shall give notice in written form (e.g. by email) and organize a doodle poll to facilitate the selection of appropriate meeting dates. The finalized meeting dates should also be known to PC and PM.

If so decided during the meeting, the chairperson may produce written minutes of each meeting which shall be the formal record of the meeting. The draft minutes shall be sent to all meeting participants, including PC and PM within 10 calendar days from sending. If no participant has objected to the chairperson within 15 calendar days after sending the draft, minutes will be considered as accepted. The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all partners, including PC and PM and GA representatives.

4. Project Reporting

ThrombUS+ has 3 reporting periods (RP). The periodic reports are being prepared with the contribution of all consortium partners, under the overall responsibility and coordination of the PC. The periodic reports should be submitted to EC within 60 days after the end of the reporting period, by the PC.

Periodic reports will be compiled by the PM based on the previous 6-month reports, corresponding to the reporting period. The PM will prepare the periodic report and send it to WPLs and the GA representatives within 30 days of after the end of the reporting period. If no WPL or GA member has objected in writing with respect to the accuracy of the yearly report within 10 calendar days, the report is considered accepted and will be finalized. The PM shall send the periodic report to all GA representatives and publish it on the project internal website. The PC shall submit the yearly report to EC within 60 days after the end of the reporting period.

4.1. Six-month internal reports

The six-month internal reports will provide the PC and GA with summarized progress of the project, with respect to targets and activities and form the basis for risk identification, analysis, and management, as well as the means to communicate officially intermediate task outcomes amongst the consortium partners. In addition, a report on performance indicators and resources/cost allocation for the reporting period will be included. The six-month internal progress report will be compiled following the respective template and will report on the following:

- Activities and outcomes accomplished during the reporting period (per Task).
- Degree of adherence to the work plan – report on delays, justification and mitigation.
- Revision requests for task work plan for the following six-months reporting period.
- Dissemination and activities tables.

- Performance indicators.
- Resources/cost allocation.

The PM will notify WPLs of the pending 6-month report 10 calendar days before the end of the reporting period. WPLs shall return their reports within 10 calendar days after the end of the reporting period (i.e. 20 days after notification). The PM will compile the 6-month report and send it to TLs, WPLs and GA members within 20 days of the end of the reporting period. If no TL, WPL or GA member has objected in writing with the accuracy to the report within 10 calendar days, the report will be accepted and will be considered finalized. The PM shall send the compiled six-month report to all consortium members and publish it on the internal file storage infrastructure.

5. Risk Management Plan

Risk management involves identifying and mitigating events that might adversely impact the project. This section elaborates on the risk management process and risks already described in DoA.

5.1. Risk Management Overview

Risk management process will follow an iterative process in line with the project’s strategic objectives and will entail three major steps: risk assessment, risk evaluation and risk mitigation processes (as presented in Figure 2).

Risk assessment involves three processes: risk identification, risk analysis, and risk description. Identification of a new risk is the responsibility of all team members and is recorded and communicated up the management structure using. Any newly identified risk is discussed and assessed in GA, and the result may lead to an update of the identified risks.

Risk evaluation will appraise the probability of each risk (low, medium, high) and will estimate the severity based on the following scale of 3 levels of perceived risk severity: high, medium and low as summarized in Table 3. Risk evaluation will take into account the potential severity as well as probability of a risk occurring during the project and will use a 3-level scale for risk classification (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Overview of risk management process.

All risks will be managed actively, accordingly to their level:

Level 1: Not acceptable risk – immediate mitigations must result in a significant improvement.

Level 2: Intermediate risk – no immediate action required but mitigations must be identified.

Level 3: Mostly acceptable risk – continue monitoring for potential change of risk level.

Level 1 and Level 2 risks must be evaluated continuously and reported to the Coordinator immediately when identified. Level 3 risks will be monitored and reported during internal progress reports or in case their level changes.

Table 3. Risk severity scale

Severity	Explanation
High	Significant impact to the project. Significant impact on the project organisation and operations. Significant impact on stakeholder engagement
Medium	Moderate impact to the project. Moderate impact on the project organisation and operations. Moderate impact on stakeholder engagement.
Low	Insignificant impact to the project. Insignificant impact on the project organisation and operations. Insignificant impact on stakeholder engagement.

		severity		
		low	medium	high
probability	high (65-100 %)	level 2 response required	level 1 immediate action	level 1 immediate action
	medium (35-65 %)	level 3 keep monitoring	level 2 response required	level 1 immediate action
	low (0-35 %)	level 3 keep monitoring	level 3 keep monitoring	level 2 response required

Figure 3. Risk assessment matrix for defining risk levels.

WP Leaders will re-evaluate risks continually and report accordingly to the Coordinator. Once a potential risk is identified a Risk Identification will be communicated to the Project Coordinator. This will include:

- Risk title/id;
- Risk short description;
- Related WP/Task;
- Severity;
- Probability;
- Classification (Figure 3);
- Proposed risk minimization measures;
- Proposed risk mitigation; and

- Mitigation acceptance implications.

In case a risk materializes, the respective WP Leader is responsible to report to GA who will decide on a specific risk mitigation procedure and communicate this via a Risk Mitigation Notification. This will include:

- Risk title/id;
- Risk short description;
- Related WP/Task;
- Risk materialization date;
- Risk mitigation; and

Mitigation acceptance implications, including potential negative impact to risks and the project.

5.2. Risk monitoring

This list of potential risks as identified in the beginning of the project will be updated and monitored during the course of the project. Each risk is linked to a Task, WP or several WPs, and a partner/person responsible for its monitoring.

All identified risks will be monitored by respective WP Leaders and the Coordinator. An update on their status, probability, severity and their status will be reported in each 6-month internal progress report and discussed within GA meetings (for decision making) and within Project Consortium meetings (for planning and implementation). Risk status possibilities are shown in Table 4.

Risk monitoring will be continuous and reported in 6-month internal reports or when a risk materializes. This will involve re-assessment of the severity, probability and status of a risk and will also include respective actions taken.

Table 4. Risk status possibilities.

Risk status	Explanation
identified	the risk has been identified and described
materialized	the risk has occurred
contained	the risk has successfully been mitigated
N/A	the risk is no longer applicable

6. Handling Necessary Changes

Although the DoA has a careful and detailed work plan, the R&I nature of the project as well as risk management may create the need for necessary changes. These may include:

- changes and/or amendments to already submitted deliverables,
- changes in the internal detailed WP/Task work plan, timetable and/or work team (which does not affect the overall Deliverable procedure),
- changes in consortium, including addition of Associate Partners; and
- major changes in DoA and Consortium which may result in Grant Agreement amendment.

In case there is a need to update a Deliverable after this has been finalized and submitted, a Change Request is submitted by the Requesting party (e.g. a partner or a project reviewer) to the GA. This describes the problem and the proposed solution. The GA requests the recommendation of the respective WP and Task Leaders and records decisions.

In case there is a need to update a detailed WP/Task work plan (internal to the WP, which does not affect project Deliverables), an informal change request is submitted by the requesting party (e.g. a partner or team member) to the WP Leader (e.g. via email). This describes the problem and the proposed solution. The WP Leader in collaboration with Task Leaders records decisions via a change notification which includes the new work plan and respective timetable. This is communicated to team members and PM/PC.

In case of a third party interested in becoming an Associated Partner to ThrombUS+, the third party submits an Associated Partner Request Form to the GA. This includes a short organization description, and suggested collaboration with ThrombUS+. Upon approval by the GA, a non-disclosure agreement is signed between the Associated Partner and ThrombUS+ Coordinator.

In case there is a need to update the DoA (which will mandate a Grant Agreement Amendment) a Change Request is submitted by the requesting party (e.g. a partner or a project reviewer) to the GA. The GA records decisions via a Change Notification which is communicated to the EC Project Officer via the Coordinator and the proper DoA amendment process as provided by Horizon rules is followed.

7. Document Management

Document management refers to the preparation and the update of template documents for the various deliverables, management reports or project's need, as well as establishing a document system, and assuring compliance with documents naming conventions. It also refers to uploading and archiving all important documents produced within the ThrombUS+ project. PM is responsible for monitoring all the above-mentioned tasks.

7.1. File editors and formats

Internal project documents will be developed primarily by Microsoft Office (version 2019 and above or Office 365). Public documentation will primarily be distributed as Acrobat PDF format. Formats to be considered for various types of documents are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Indicative documents expected to be produced and the corresponding file formats and editors to be used.

Type and intended use	Format	Production tool
Documents intended for internal project activities Draft versions deliverables Draft versions of all project's documents	.docx	Microsoft Word
Presentations intended for internal project activities	.pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint
Documents and presentations intended for external communication and the website Final versions of deliverables Final versions of all project documents and presentations Documents available on the website	.pdf	Any software tools that can produce .pdf files, including the 'save as' function in MS Office tools
Images	.jpeg, .png, etc	Any software tool that can produce respective files
Compressed files/folders	.zip	Any software tool than can produce .zip files

7.2. Document naming conventions and version control

Document management will be ensured by tracking the history of changes with the following project documents:

- deliverables,
- project/WP meetings agendas and minutes,
- GA and consortium meetings agendas and minutes,
- project events agendas,
- official reports to the EC,
- documents, such as contact lists, mailing lists and internal effort reporting,
- documents used for internal project management and monitoring purposes, and
- materials/publications produced by the project, such as commentaries, policy briefs, working documents, presentations, and newsletters.

To ease the communication process, document sharing within consortium members and reviewing, partners are advised to use naming conventions based on self-explanatory titles and versions. A history of changes of each document should be stored within the document. All deliverables should include a table describing the different versions of the document and the reasons for change/update. The 1st version submitted to EC should always be _v1. The naming conventions for the draft deliverable ready for internal review, and the revised deliverable after internal review, are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Naming conventions for the Thrombus+ deliverables

Name	Thrombus_DY.X_vA.BB or Thrombus_DY.X_vA.BB-IN
Y	Work package number
Y	Deliverable number within this work package
A	Major version of the deliverable. Version v1 will always be the version to be initially submitted to the EC. Version 0 will be the first draft version.
BB	Minor version of the deliverable for updates during the preparation phase. The first version will be v0.01.
IN	Initials of the reviewer's name - for files with tracked changes and comments by reviewers

7.3. Document internal exchange and archiving

Deliverables submitted to the EC are in pdf format and should be stored within the MS Teams files data storage infrastructure in both the original (.docx) and portable (.pdf) formats. If a deliverable is of sensitive nature (SEN), a publishable version (in pdf format) of the submitted deliverables should be created if it is feasible, and this will be archived within the same directory. Publishable versions will be uploaded to project's official website <http://www.thrombus.eu/> for dissemination purposes.

7.4. Document Templates

During the Thrombus+ project, 52 deliverables (plus 4 deliverables pertaining to ethics requirements) and several other documents will be produced. For this reason, several document templates have been created. These templates will be updated constantly according to the project's needs and are shared to all consortium's members through the project's file sharing infrastructure.

8. Unique identifiers

The project outcomes and all related technical information and documentation, such as individual software and hardware components, use cases, user requirements, functional and technical specifications will use a project wide unique identification system, to be managed by the PC/PM.